

1 Graphical Abstract

2 Spatio-temporal analysis of A/H5N1 outbreaks in cats in Poland combining the evidence from official data, citizens reports and media interest

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Interpolated daily series of signals

6 Highlights

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- 10 • the A/H5N1 was already probably circulating in cats in second half of May 2023 in regions
11 bordering with Ukraine and this information could be missing without extending surveillance
12 to non official sources, so some other approaches without phylodynamic-spatio-temporal
13 analytic of multiple sources may lead to wrong epidemiological conclusions
- 14 • most of positive cases form chains structure both on bird migration paths and close to high
15 abundance of nesting sites of water birds, thus We recommend to perform active monitoring
16 (molecular and serology) of water birds in Pomerania and selected sites in Western Poland
17 (as maybe some low viral pressure of active virus is still present at the end of July 2023).

Spatio-temporal analysis of A/H5N1 outbreaks in cats in Poland combining the evidence from official data, citizens reports and media interest

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Abstract

One Health topics such as transmission of zoonotic agents of domestic/wild birds and environmental residue problems, food and feed safety become increasingly important to modern society in the post pandemic times. We performed phylodynamic-spatio-temporal analysis of A/H5N1 epizootic in cats in Poland in Spring-Summer 2023 based on: 1) 30 (positive) and 27 (negative) cases from WOAHI reference lab, 2) suspected 87 cases submitted by animal owners (participatory epidemiology), 3) daily time series of i) Google queries for Avian Influenza (AI), cats disease and cats deaths, as well as ii) mentions of cat/cats and AI in social and traditional media; 19 RNA sequences of viruses; Data triangulation suggests the most likely scenarios based on Google queries, news and social media analysis, reference lab results and participatory epidemiology reports: 1) The first A/H5N1 cases were probably in cats in late May near the south-eastern border (based on the evidence from the retrospective media analysis and participatory reports). 2) The highest disease burden was in Pomerania (particularly Gdansk) in mid-June. 3) The highest positivity ratio was in Western Poland, indicating outbreak clusters in late June/early July. 4) Positive cases formed clear chains, supporting the environmental source hypotheses (on the connection to bird migration paths and nearness of nesting sites of water birds). 5) There are at least 2 (eastern and western Poland) separate genetic clusters of viruses. We recommend active serological/PCR monitoring in both water birds and environment in Gdańsk and some sites in Greater Poland area (probably there is still small viral pressure as the cases were in August). Even that hypothesis of poultry meat (being feed for cats) contamination, seems to be unlikely (i.e. our method indicated that positive cases situated far from bird migratory paths were wrongly geocoded), aviary disease surveillance system needs to be updated to handle with new pandemic threats.

Keywords: infectious disease modelling, phylodynamics, spatio-temporal analysis, avian influenza, zoonotic disease of poultry

1. Introduction

Avian influenza (AI), particularly highly pathogenic (HPAI) subtypes A/H5 is deadly (depending on bird species) and contagious disease of poultry and free living birds, being subject to mandatory eradication in European Union (EU). HPAI pose a serious threat to poultry industry and due to zoonotic/spillovers potential [1] also to other species (including humans), therefore the risk of virus (re-) emergence in environment and farms should be minimised. The main route of

52 introducing the virus into Poland since 2020 is seasonal migration of wild birds [2]. Here, we report
53 on the detection of spillover of A/H5N1 to cats during spring/summer 2023 in Poland. Isolated
54 viruses from cats after 18.06.2023 in Poland belong to clade 2.3.4.4b and cluster with virus strains
55 from birds sampled in Central Europe from late 2022 onwards [3, 4] and were found in wild birds
56 thought spring/summer 2023 in Poland. Between May (26.05 Kętrzyn: Warmian-Masurian) and
57 July (01.07 Kraków: Lower Poland) there were no outbreaks of AI in domestic poultry in 2023
58 (these mentioned are from different strains).

59 1.1. *Cats and birds in Poland*

60 From last few years of observation the common risk areas of AI in wild birds include usually
61 eastern and western parts of the country, and in particular, areas located within the territory of
62 Greater Poland, Pomerania and Kuyavian-Pomeranian from the west and Subcarpatian, Lublin
63 and Warmian-Masurian from the east [2]. By comparing locations of AI outbreaks in wild birds
64 and poultry farms with risk factors (i.e. density of waterfowls) a significant spatial correlation was
65 recorded [5]. Terrestrial and aquatic wild birds are the usually the primary source of outbreaks
66 in domestic poultry, however clustering patterns demonstrate that secondary spread also played a
67 role in high-density hubs of production in Greater Poland and Masovia regions [6].

68 The total population of on farms ($\tilde{2}M$) and domestic cats ($\tilde{2}M$) in Poland is about 4 million
69 [7, 8] which shows that less than every third household in Poland has a cat [9]. This means that
70 the density of cats per number of inhabitants is about 1.5-2 times lower than the European average
71 [8]. Cats may be expose to the AI viruses directly by interactions with birds (i.e. hunting), or
72 indirectly by contact with contaminated environment (i.e. formits or feed brought by humans to
73 home).

74 75 76 77 78 1.2. *Related works on current outbreak*

79 Rabalski et al. [3] involved a participatory approach with animal owners self-report and
80 included in phylogeny analysis isolates obtained from non-reference labs collected without sani-
81 tary/veterinary supervision. (which without understanding how the concept of infodemics could
82 lead to wrong conclusions about distribution and cause of the infections). On the other hand,
83 Domańska et al. [4] used the reference laboratory positive cases as the material (which without
84 spatio-temporal context and non-including negative results could lead to missing important clus-
85 tering and path forming patterns). Both approaches are complementary, but a kind of integrative
86 approach is missing to incorporate strong and weak sides of each dataset. The authors [4, 3]
87 adopted a number of simplifications, which should be justified, as papers may reach a wide audi-
88 ence and may be cited by one health community or journalists. Thus, no attempt has been made
89 up to submission of this article to carry out a quantitative spatio-temporal-genetic assessment
90 of the risk of virus introduction. In today's globally interconnected anthropocentric ecosystem,
91 outbreaks of zoonotic disease can spread widely and cause considerable impact on ONE public
92 health [10]. Added benefits of the multi-source space-time-phylogenetic vs only space, only time,
93 only genetic modeling of epidemiological data (current state of the art) has been recently raised
94 in epidemiological community [11].

94 1.3. *research aims*

Objective of comparative analysis and interpretation of data to determine:

- Triangulated distribution of diseases in time and space with genetic inference
- Presence or absence of disease

- 95
- source detection

96 Understanding the dynamics of spreading pathogen in geographical space is of critical impor-
97 tance for source detection and such kind of models already allowed to timely identification of the
98 outbreak's origin (i.e. food-borne outbreak of EHEC in Germany [12, 13], inferred transmission
99 chains of SARS-COV-2 in humans [14]). However, predicting the phylodynamic-spatio-temporal
100 evolution remains challenging as the process is shaped by environmental interactions, flows of birds,
101 humans and feed, topology, spreading non-linearities, and heterogeneous adaptation behavior of
102 cat owners

103 2. Data and methods

104 The results are presented using:

- 105 • phylogeny matrices with epidemiological inference;
- 106 • descriptive and exploratory analyses (as partially performed by [3, 4])
- 107 • time series approach as auto/cross-correlations and calculation of the epidemic curve charac-
108 teristics. By inferring the lagged time series of events (positive and negative results, suspected
109 cases and social interest), we can improve the accuracy of key epidemiological parameters [15].
110 Temporal dynamics and Spatio-temporal clusters can explain disease transmission occurring
111 through local and long-distance spread [16, 17].
- 112 • a risk (and relative risk) map, clustering (k-mean and dbSCAN [18]) developed using Geo-
113 graphic Information System (GIS);
- 114 • spatio-temporal distribution of queries for cats health and AI related topics. Digital epidemi-
115 ology approach is widely used, for example, “infoveillance” as a term comes from information
116 surveillance [19].
- 117 • phylodynamic-spatio-temporal matrices and clustering [11].

118 All analyses (except some media interest spatio-temporal transformation with media listing
119 tools as EventRegistry.org and Brand24.com [20] are fully reproducible as well as all data and
120 recipes (with much more extended analysis) are available [21, 22, 23].

121 2.1. Participatory sample

122 Some activists started community-based surveillance/ participatory epidemiology [20] in social
123 media (a phenomenon popular in Poland since COVID-19 pandemic [24, 25]). unofficial data -
124 suspected 87 case submitted by animal owners. Here, we take the date of symptoms developing
125 into account (from 15.06 to 08.07).

126 2.2. WOAHA reference lab

127 According international regulations [26] on infectious disease control (particularly HPAI), the
128 National Veterinary Research Institute in Puławy is responsible for testing materials from animals
129 Thus we process official data (from reference lab) in an area of Poland (testing date from 22.06 to
130 10.07). It consists of 30 cases (positive results) and 27 controls (negative results). Here, we take
131 the date of laboratory test into account (extended discussion on the choice and its consequences
132 is available [22])

133 2.3. Infodemiology

134 Variable "GT interest [27]" is daily time series mean across AI, cats disease and cats deaths
135 queries. Google Trends monitoring (on both national and voievodship level) can be extremely
136 beneficial for tracking trends, understanding public demand of information.

137 Variable "media interest" is daily time series sum of mentions cat/cats and AI, cats in social
138 and traditional media. Media listening involves tracking mentions of specific topics in the media
139 (here related both to AI and cats health) and show that is the supply of information (mainly local
140 news portals and agencies [28]). This can help to stay informed about the latest public perceptions,
141 and potential crises. Brand24 was used for that goal.

142 Both tools allow for a real time listening [29] and collect information before the official surveil-
143 lance started or after participatory epidemiology lost attention in reporting (for full time span
144 15.05-12.07).

145 2.4. Phylogeny to find the strain ancestors

146 To trace back the feline strains, we performed the phylogenetic analysis (see Fig.1), which
147 included:

148 1) Extracting the possibly related strains from GISAID; we included all the avian strains from
149 Jan, 2022 to Aug, 2023 from Africa, Asia, North and South Americas;

150 2) Aligning avian strains on the feline ones using MAFFT to obtain the SNPs typical for the
151 feline ones;

152 3) Building a phylogenetic tree using Neighbourhood-joining algorithm (NJ);

153 4) Obtain the cluster of strains that have minimal phylogenetic distance to the feline strains;

154 5) Analyse the proportions of different strain sources (birds, countries).

155 This analysis was performed for each gene of the influenza virus: HA, NA, PB1, PB2, MP, NS,
156 NP. Those genes were analysed separately since it is known that they can evolve independently.

157 2.5. Birds migration routes

158 After obtaining the group of strains, which were the closest to the feline ones, we performed
159 the analysis of birds migration routes (see Fig.1). All the birds, which were carrying the suspicious
160 samples, were considered as potential strain delivers, so their migration routes were mapped on
161 each other to see if they could have any common areas to exchange and reassert the viral strains. In
162 addition, we have labeled the places where the samples were taken to align them to the migration
163 route.

164 We assumed that the migration routes did not change dramatically during the observation
165 period (2022-2023).

166 3. Results

167 Until about 18.06 [20] we have a local discussion in Gdańsk (at least there are traces of it
168 on Facebook) and interest in the environment of veterinarians [Fig. 2]. On June 19, the case
169 gained momentum of a nationwide dimension (specialists and local Pomeranian media publicized
170 the situation).

171 Since the disclosure of information about the alleged contamination of poultry meat with the
172 A / H5N1 virus on June 29 [30], at a high level, the Veterinary Inspection's activities have finally
173 started in full swing, because it affects the poultry industry, which is very important for the Polish
174 economy, and "central control" has been turned on (certainly good from the information point of
175 view), but perhaps not epidemiologically.

Figure 1: Phylogenetic and migration routes analysis pipeline

Figure 2: Time evolution of the epizootic and infodemic

176 Due to the infodemic risks, the flow of information in the context of the H5N1 avian influenza
 177 situation was monitored by state and poultry organizations [30, 31]. Thus, certain stakeholders of
 178 the system could introduce mal/mis-information [32].

179 Based on all sources separately (all of which have their advantages and disadvantages) quite
 180 different conclusions can be stated, so an integrative framework is missing. For instance Rabalski
 181 et al., [3] did not attempt to differentiate signal from noise in citizens' databases [31, 33, 29, 21]
 182 Interpolated daily dynamics of positive case, suspected cases from participatory study, normalized
 183 interest in Google trends and No articles/post on the issue per million citizen in media suggest

184 that the epizootic and infodemic have already passed the peak phase and is in the ending phase
185 [fig. 2]. Variables "googles and media interest" are derivatives across AI, cats disease and cats
186 deaths queries. However, upon submission of the article, there are still some individual positive
187 case, which mean that the outbreak is not over.

188 3.1. Spatial

189 We see that all cats materials (together +/-, but mainly negative) and participatory reports
190 are sampled moreover from general cats population (according to human population density) with
bias towards city cats [fig. 3].

Cases (+) and control (-) and participatory epidemiology

Figure 3: Geographical distribution of + and negative - laboratory cases of cats or ill suspected from participatory results

191 From a first look it seems to be in line with the water bird migration and nesting areas at the
192 water reservoir routes [23]:
193

- 194 • north-south line along the Nysa Kłodzka, Oder, Warta and Vistula rivers;
- 195 • north-east line of the Vistula and Bug basin.

196 Under-representation of positive clusters in the most populated metropolies in Poland (Upper-
197 Silesia agglomeration, Warsaw, Krakow, Łódź and Szczecin at least in reference lab data) suggests
198 that human travels (with or without cats) doesn't play a role in the epidemic spread.

199 The spatially-varying probability of different type of point (positive and negative) using kernel
200 smoothing suggest that the positivity ratio in Western Poland is a few times higher than in rest
201 of the country [22].

202 The highest social interest was observed in Pomerania and secondary in Kuyavian-Pomeranian
203 and Lower Silesia [fig. 4]. Moreover, the most common geographical places till so called risk
204 assessment phase [fig. 2] mentioned in the media were Gdańsk, Lublin, Poznań, Bydgoszcz [20].

Suspected cases per mil cit

Confirmed cases per mil cit

Interest in Google

Figure 4: Geographical distribution of the cases and the interest normalized **source? which year?** by population size) across Polish voivodships.

Data	1NN	2NN
Positive cases	0.18	0.30
Negative cases	0.38	0.65
Citizen reports	0.20	0.36

Table 1:

205 Positive data points have smaller ANN than suspected (even there is much less of them) and
 206 than negative results, thus it suggests that positive cases form some characteristics chains [tab. 1].
 207 This support migratory bird cause of outbreak.

208 We see that social interest is strictly spatially correlated with participatory engagement [23].

209 3.2. Temporal

210 Lagged-correlation analysis suggests that citizens reports are one week ahead the positive cases.
 211 Interest in Google trends and in media is one week after positive cases [23].

212 The shape of the pseudo-epidemic curve of participatory reports is not symmetric [fig. 5]. One
 213 of the possible non-biological explanation is that people lost their attention in the beginning of
 214 July (Since July 8, no new cases were reported). The peak of submission reports (by symptoms
 215 developments) was around 14-17.06.

216 Among the fist portion of samples analyzed by WOAHI reference lab 80% were positive. The
 217 positiviy ratio went down to 20% till the end of interested period [22] and the deceasing trend is
 218 ongoing upon submission of this article.

219 By analysis of smoothed epidemic curve of positive results [fig. 5] and cumulative distribution
 220 [22], the peak of outbreak (by testing time) was around 27-30.06. The left arm of epidemic curve
 221 is missing. Possible biological explanation is that due to nesting time and need to feed offsprings,
 222 the wild birds penetrate bigger areas (bigger exposure for cats and human mechanical vectors).
 223 The non-biological possible explanation is that surveillence started when the outbreak was already
 224 after the peak.

225 Temporal correlations between series showed that there is de-synchronization between partici-
 226 patory reporting and supply/demand information needs.

Smoothed positive cases and suspected (from citizens) intensity ii

Figure 5: Smoothed (pseudo)-epidemic curves

227 3.3. Phylogeny and migration route analysis to find the ancestors

228 19 samples from WOA reference [4] lab (from cats only) proved that there are at least 2
 229 separate sources of infections (one in Western Poland and second dispersed around the country).

230 =====

231 The phylogenetic analysis revealed the group of phylogenetically close alleles in wild and do-
 232 mestic birds in Africa, Asia and Europe for each gene (Suppl. fig. 1). Regardless of potential
 233 independence in the evolutionary process, most genes in feline strains had the same alleles as the
 234 avian strains from Middle East and Africa in most genes (see Table 2), including HA, NA and

Figure 6: Migration routes and samples

235 PB2. These alleles were found in different, mostly wild, bird strains in Israel, Egypt and Gambia.
 236 The carrying birds were mostly those that migrate during the year. The phylogenetic distance
 237 between feline and these African/Middle Eastern alleles was minimal, so they can be considered
 238 as a group of delivers to Europe.

239 To summarize the alleles movement through Africa and Middle East to Europe, we mapped
 240 the samples on the migration routes of the birds species which carried the alleles. (see Fig.)

241 However, the phylogenetical analysis did not reveal the African/Middle Eastern samples which
 242 carried the close to feline NP allele. Surprisingly, this allele was found extensively presented across
 243 domestic and wild birds in Europe (see Table 3).

244 3.4. Spatio- Temporal

245 There is small bit consistent gradient between positive cases and participatory results between
 246 time and geography from East to West (-0.20 for reports+; -0.21 for citizens) and from South to
 247 North (0.23 for reports+; 0.16 for citizens), but not significant [23]. Temporal correlations between
 248 series on voivodeship level showed that there is de-synchronization between participatory reporting
 249 and supply/ demand information needs [23].

250 There is clear spatio-temporal cluster of suspected cases in second part of Mai on Lublin/Podkarpacie
 251 area [fig. 9]. Time gives no additional information (in terms of quality of clustering) in reference
 252 lab positive cases.

253 In the in statu nascendi analysis [22] only the case of the Caracal of Lodz did not fit (wrongly
 254 coded place by veterinary inspection) and this analysis allowed to find this error. For negative
 255 cases, the Silesian cluster is mainly FIV/FELV and the Mazovian cluster is driven by other diseases
 256 causing symptoms (mainly neurological) imitating AI.

Figure 7: Hierarchical matrixes of SNPs distances: among 19 samples from WOA reference lab [4] ; 11 samples with environmental one [3]

Samples 1 “A.environment.Poland.Kra1.2023” and 11 A.cat.Poland.Kra1.2023.” from [3] are from suspected cat case and its feed (poultry meat), which never been confirmed by WOA reference lab.

There are no clear separate clusters for the small sample from [3], which can lead to wrong conclusions (as authors didn’t have big enough sample to see potential different sources). The cat meat case from the Kraków area is clustered with the Gdańsk subcluster. Moreover, Lublin region cases (from eastern Poland) mixes well with cases from Western Poland, which also made an illusion of dispersed outbreak.

In the *in situ* nastendi analysis [23] we speculated, that virus found in meat in Krakow area (meat bought in beginning of June: “A.environment.Poland.Kra1.2023”) should be close to (if our hypothesis of introduction thought Lublin/border area is valid) early cases from Lublin and difference in SNPs is less than 4.

Isolate ID	Host	Place	Date	Gene
EPI_ISL_18847168	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	Egypt	2022-12-21	HA, NA, NS, MP, PB2
EPI_ISL_13658359	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	Israel	2022-01-02	PB1, PB2, MP
EPI_ISL_13465456	<i>Pelecanus onocrotalus</i>	Israel	2021-11-29	PB1, PB2, MP
EPI_ISL_13477015	<i>Gallus domesticus</i>	Israel	2022-01-09	PB1, PB2, MP
EPI_ISL_13068727	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	Israel	2021-12-15	PB1, PB2, MP
EPI_ISL_13609610	<i>Pelecanus onocrotalus</i>	Israel	2022-01-12	PB1, PB2, MP
EPI_ISL_18127710- EPI_ISL_18127714	<i>Wild birds</i>	Gambia	2023-04-01	PB1, PB2, MP

Table 2: Cluster of African/Middle Eastern samples close to feline ones (HA, NA, NS, MP, PB1, PB2 gene alleles).
any phylogenetic trees?

Isolate ID	Host	Place	Date	Gene
EPI_ISL_18033422	<i>Gallus domesticus</i>	Poland	2023-06-29	NP
EPI_ISL_17978700	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	Poland	2023-06-04	NP
EPI_ISL_18432788	<i>Gallus domesticus</i>	Germany	2023-05-22	NP
EPI_ISL_18032446	<i>Anas sp.</i>	Poland	2022-12-15	NP
EPI_ISL_18032447	<i>Anser anser</i>	Poland	2022-12-17	NP
EPI_ISL_18032445	<i>Cygnus olor</i>	Poland	2023-02-14	NP

Table 3: Cluster of European samples close to feline NP allele

XYTT reference lab +

XYTT participatory samp

Figure 8: K-means clustering

257 Spatial Clusters of negative cases are more integrated and hierarchical than for positives ones
 258 [fig. 9, tab. 4], which may be artefact of catching clusters of infectious diseases with similar
 259 symptoms. This definitely must be taken into account in interpretation of participatory reports
 260 [3]. High betweenness and Sum of squares of spatio-temporal clustering of positive cases [tab. 4]
 261 in comparison to negative cases and participatory reports (after taking into account different size

Data	betweenness	sum of squares
Positive cases	5.49	6.14
Negative cases	3.71	4.84
Citizen reports	6.49	9.67

Table 4: K-mean statistics in XYT normalized model

262 of sample) suggests positive points are ordered in some kind of chains (i.e. corridors for wild birds
263 movement).

264 3.5. *phylogenetic - Spatio- Temporal*

265 Genetic virus data with associated information about location and time (of testing not sam-
266 pling unfortunately) offer opportunities to reconstruct how pathogens have spread in Polish cat's
267 population [34]. We propose to combine Euclidean distance for XY (space) and T (time) in nor-
268 malized unites with additional layer of SNPs counts distance of viruses for 19 cases for each full
269 information is available.

270 We see that a single Poznan case (upper left corner [fig. 9]) is from a separated introduction of
271 virus. One big blocking cluster of Western Poland can be seen (with one linking case from a Lublin
272 region close to subcluster of cases from Gdańsk). However, links between Gdańsk metropolitan
273 area and other regions maybe explained by being touristic destination hot-spot in the summer [35].

274 Weakly connected cluster of Lublin cases is complementing the hierarchical matrix.

275 Clustering is the unsupervised action of collecting points with similar characteristics and to-
276 gether with classification task is the core of machine learning techniques. According to DBSCAN
277 there are 3 clear clusters (sensitive to choice of weights in inference model [fig. 11]). First is a
278 single case in Poznan, second western Poland and third Lublin area. Second and third clusters
279 are interlinked. Concluding, sequences formed one distinctive cluster (in Western Poland) and
280 two interlinked clusters (clear Western and mix of Eastern and Western) and each originated from
281 different (re-)introductions of the pathogen that occurred probably in spring 2023 (exact time can
282 be determined with MAP technique [36]). We see strong sensitivity to the choice of the weight of
283 different layers (spatial, temporal and genetic) or fixed number of clusters [23].

284 4. Conclusions

285 If one can take into account possible biased of each method then, data triangulation suggest that
286 most likely (according to the Google and media analysis, reference lab results and participatory
287 epidemiology):

- 288 • the first cases A/H5N1 were probably in cats in second half of May in regions bordering with
289 Ukraine (possible meat and wild life sources). This information could be missing without
290 retrospective media analysis and participatory reporting;
- 291 • the biggest burden of disease was in Pomerania (in particular in Gdansk) in the middle of
292 June;
- 293 • positivity ratio is the highest in Western Poland as well as western Poland form a sepearete
294 phylogenetic-spatio-temporal cluster, which suggest that the last outbreak clusters were
295 in end June/beginning of July in north-Western Poland;

Figure 9: Hierarchical matrix of phylogenetic-spatio-temporal distances among 19 samples

- 296 • the positive cases are clearly forming chains (in contradiction to negative cases and to partici-
297 patory reports) which support environmental source hypothesizes;
- 298 • poultry meat contamination as additional factor of spread would explain some additional
299 transmissions (i.e. caracal case in Łódź or cannot be easily explained by environmen-
300 tal exposure and this case was found to be wrongly geocoded or possible case in Cracow need deeper
301 investigation).
- 302 • Trajectory of main events [fig. 2] in outbreak investigation (since mid May till mid July and

Figure 10: Dbscan clusters of phylodynamic-spatio-temporal distances among 19 samples

Figure 11: Dbscan clusters of phylodynamic-spatio-temporal distances among 19 samples

303 still individual cases reported till submission of the article) suggest environmental long-term
 304 exposure.

305 Based on plausible assumptions on the phylodynamic-spatio-temporal structure of the national
 306 epizootic on triangulated date, the approach can suggest localization the multiple origin of the
 307 outbreaks in border area with Ukraine and Western Poland. Phylo-tempo- geographic inference
 308 attempts to estimate chance transition between points and clusters with 3 infections paths identified
 309 [fig. 11]. Thus, probably the problem is wider (not-geographically limited to Poland), and active
 310 molecular and serological monitoring of AI wild bird in central Europe is welcomed. Especially
 311 among aquatic birds, for which course of A/H5 is not as deadly as for terrestrial ones. For migratory
 312 bird networks some kind of sentinel can provide the times at which they detect the spread of viruses
 313 [37].

314 There are few limitations that we want to explicitly mention. First, the source identification
 315 and clustering methods is only as precise as data it relies on. The level of noise in participatory
 316 and infoveillance is huge. Moreover, sampling of cats for laboratory is strongly biased (i.e. no

317 clear rules were provided from Polish CVO) spatially (i.e. some cluster of other cats diseased were
318 detected) and temporally (i.e. changing in time "social pressure" on veterinary service). Secondly,
319 the clustering models calibration was performed in *statu nascendi* mode, thus sensitive analysis for
320 parameter choice (i.e. weights of different layers) should be done. Our method also may indicate
321 imported cases and paths of local transmissions although this is not perfect since there is always
322 a probability that i.e. food-borne source could imitate spatio-temporally chains of genetically
323 different different strains by chance.

324 4.1. *Water bird migration and nesting*

325
326 We suggest water birds serological active sampling (i.e. from hunting) in Lubelskie province
327 (probably there is no more viral pressure as the peak of cases was probably in May).

328 The hypothesis to be verified is that the most of positive cases form chains both on bird
329 migration paths and close to high abundance of nesting sites of water birds.

330 Some migration routes in middle/late Spring (before nesting season) are more less known [23].
331 As well as geographical abundance of species or nesting site can be found in birds atlas or citizens
332 participatory ornithological projects [23].

333 4.2. *Meat food chains analysis*

334 We propose an analysis of possible contamination of meat/eggs imported from Ukraine or from
335 farms/slaughterhouses in Lubelskie province from May (if founded). In retrospect, the collection
336 and structured recording of all necessary detailed data relating to supply relationships of a sample
337 of poultry meat found to be positive [3] is know to be the most difficult task of tracing [13]. However,
338 example of supply chains can be easily found in the Internet [23] and are available in ministry of
339 agriculture registry. If the supply network is know, current development of algorithms [37, 38]
340 allow for detection the source (of course if unlikely meat hypothesis is real).

341 4.3. *Extended epidemiological analysis*

342 We recommend to perform active monitoring (molecular and serology) of water birds in Pomera-
343 nia and selected sites in Western Poland (as maybe some low viral pressure of active virus is still
344 present at the end of July 2023). Retrospective investigation of south-eastern border area should
345 be done to verify if Lublin cases are the origin of the outbreak. Possible excess mortality rates
346 from veterinary clinics in May on Polish Ukrainian border should be analyzed [39].

347 Regression analysis for risk factors among positive and negative results should be performed.
348 Such a study would report on the spatio-temporal dynamics and the factors that might have
349 influenced A/H5N1 in cats that will be estimated in Poland.

350 4.4. *preparedness for future outbreaks*

351 Measures of control and prevention as well as outbreak investigation in response A/H5N1 in
352 mammals differs significantly between counties in EU (compare Poland [3] vs Finland [40]) as
353 well as intra-country (i.e. Gdańsk metropolitan area vs other regions of Poland). We found
354 that surveillance communication standards for WOA and WHO/FAO are the most efficient,
355 while ECDC/EFSA (i.e. due to multiple errors in their communicates, not being possible to use
356 electronic disease information system for cats as a host of AI).

357 We proved, that in case of not-known disease or spillover of known disease to a new host the
358 European Surveillance System (i.e. acting in Poland) is inefficient and needs reorganisation for
359 future threats. This mean that strong national and regional Veterinary and Sanitary authorities

360 are the key resources for new threats [41]. We recommend to shift more responsibilities from ECDC
361 or EFSA to national and sub-national one health centres (with funds and possibility of acting).
362 Thus, national Epidemic Intelligence System aims at identifying, monitoring and analyzing signals
363 of sanitary dangers in human/animal/plant health threatening the Polish territory, in order to
364 produce sanitary information for:

- 365 • risk assessment (surveillance and monitoring, data collection and integration)
- 366 • risk management (infectious disease modelling from a data science perspective, investigating
367 the impact of climate change and proposing innovations for building of One Health sys-
368 tems across regions on NUTS-2 level [42]). Health intelligence [43] with use of surveillance
369 and other data can minimize cost of human engagement in microbiological workload (i.e.
370 unnecessary massive testing).
- 371 • risk communications (information on professional and laic channels)

372 For VOC (variants of concern) of Influenza (maybe in a bigger panel of other important pathogens),
373 besides wild bird and poultry farms testing sites, environmental, human and accompanying animals
374 in contact, meat inspection records could be tapped into to develop a surveillance system that
375 captures health threats information in ONE health setup [44].

376 Acknowledgement

377 AJ and VB were partially funded by the German Research Foundation for COVINT project
378 (458528774) and OptimAgent project. Thanks for discussion with colleagues from Polish Sanitary
379 and Veterinary Inspection, National Veterinary Institute in Puławy, Veterinarians in the field,
380 biomedical practitioners in Society of Health Hygiene (Epiguard Poland), cat owners as well as for
381 mathematical hints from faculty members or Institute of Veterinary Epidemiology and Biostatistics,
382 FU-Berlin, and RKI Berlin.

383 References

- 384 [1] T.-N. Carp, Expression of Concern With Regards to the Current Stages of Avian Influenza A
385 (H5N1) Zoonotic Spillover Into Humans (2023).
- 386 [2] A. Gierak, K. Śmietanka, The impact of selected risk factors on the occurrence of highly
387 pathogenic avian influenza in commercial poultry flocks in Poland, *Journal of veterinary
388 research* 65 (1) (2021) 45.
- 389 [3] L. Rabalski, A. Milewska, A. Pohlmann, K. Gackowska, T. Lepionka, K. Szczepa-
390 niak, A. Swiatalska, I. Sieminska, Z. Arent, M. Beer, M. Koopmans, M. Grzybek,
391 K. Pyrc, Emergence and potential transmission route of avian influenza A (H5N1)
392 virus in domestic cats in Poland, June 2023, *Eurosurveillance* 28 (31) (Aug. 2023).
393 doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2023.28.31.2300390.
394 URL [https://www.eurosurveillance.org/content/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2023.28.
395 31.2300390](https://www.eurosurveillance.org/content/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2023.28.31.2300390)
- 396 [4] K. Domańska-Blicharz, E. Świętoń, A. Świątalska, I. Monne, A. Fusaro, K. Tarasiuk,
397 K. Wyrostek, N. Styś-Fijoł, A. Giza, M. Pietruk, B. Zechchin, A. Pastori, Adaszek,

- 398 M. Pomorska-Mól, G. Tomczyk, C. Terregino, S. Winiarczyk, Outbreak of highly pathogenic
399 avian influenza A(H5N1) clade 2.3.4.4b virus in cats, Poland, June to July 2023, *Eurosurveil-*
400 *lance* 28 (31) (Aug. 2023). doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2023.28.31.2300366.
401 URL [https://www.eurosurveillance.org/content/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2023.28.](https://www.eurosurveillance.org/content/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2023.28.31.2300366)
402 31.2300366
- 403 [5] A. Gierak, L. Bocian, K. Smietanka, Identification of areas at increased risk of highly
404 pathogenic avian influenza occurrence, *Avian Diseases* (2019).
- 405 [6] K. Śmietanka, E. Świętoń, K. Wyrastek, E. Kozak, K. Tarasiuk, N. Styś-Fijoł, K. Dziadek,
406 K. Niemczuk, Highly pathogenic avian influenza h5n1 in poland in 2020/2021: A descriptive
407 epidemiological study of a large-scale epidemic, *Journal of Veterinary Research* 66 (1) (2022)
408 1–7.
- 409 [7] D. Krauze-Gryz, J. Gryz, M. Żmihorski, Cats kill millions of vertebrates in polish farmland
410 annually, *Global Ecology and Conservation* 17 (2019) e00516.
- 411 [8] FEDIAF, Annual report cats and dogs 2022, Tech. rep. (2023).
412 URL [https://europeanpetfood.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/](https://europeanpetfood.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Annual-Report-2022-2.pdf)
413 [Annual-Report-2022-2.pdf](https://europeanpetfood.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Annual-Report-2022-2.pdf)
- 414 [9] Landgeist, cat ownership in europe, Tech. rep. (2023).
415 URL <https://landgeist.com/2023/04/29/cat-ownership-in-europe/>
- 416 [10] S. Y. Essack, Environment: the neglected component of the one health triad, *The Lancet*
417 *Planetary Health* 2 (6) (2018) e238–e239.
- 418 [11] Future of disease modeling (in the time of ai technology and big data), OpenGeoHub Foun-
419 dation, https://doi.org/10.5446/s_1468. doi:10.5446/s_1468.
420 URL https://doi.org/10.5446/s_1468
- 421 [12] J. Manitz, T. Kneib, M. Schlather, D. Helbing, D. Brockmann, Origin detection during food-
422 borne disease outbreaks—a case study of the 2011 ehec/hus outbreak in germany, *PLoS currents*
423 6.
- 424 [13] B. Appel, EHEC outbreak 2011: Investigation of the outbreak along the food chain, BfR,
425 2012.
- 426 [14] L. Wang, X. Didelot, J. Yang, G. Wong, Y. Shi, W. Liu, G. F. Gao, Y. Bi, Inference of
427 person-to-person transmission of covid-19 reveals hidden super-spreading events during the
428 early outbreak phase, *Nature communications* 11 (1) (2020) 5006.
- 429 [15] A. Jarynowski, M. Wójta-Kempa, V. Belik, Trends in interest of COVID-19 on Polish Internet,
430 *Epidemiol Rev* 74 (2) (2020) 106–123.
- 431 [16] P. S. Ekong, E. Ducheyne, T. E. Carpenter, O. A. Owolodun, A. T. Oladokun, L. H. Lom-
432 bin, D. Berkvens, Spatio-temporal epidemiology of highly pathogenic avian influenza (h5n1)
433 outbreaks in nigeria, 2006–2008, *Preventive veterinary medicine* 103 (2-3) (2012) 170–177.

- 434 [17] R. P. Inward, F. Jackson, A. Dasgupta, G. Lee, A. L. Battle, K. V. Parag, M. U. Kraemer,
435 Impact of spatiotemporal heterogeneity in covid-19 disease surveillance on epidemiological
436 parameters and case growth rates, *Epidemics* 41 (2023) 100627. doi:10.1016/j.epidem.
437 2022.100627.
438 URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1755436522000676>
- 439 [18] Ö. PASİN, H. ANKARALI, Usage of kernel k means and dbscan cluster algorithms in health
440 studies an application (2015).
- 441 [19] G. Eysenbach, How to fight an infodemic: the four pillars of infodemic management, *Journal*
442 *of medical Internet research* 22 (6) (2020) e21820, publisher: JMIR Publications Inc., Toronto,
443 Canada.
- 444 [20] A. Jarynowski, H5n1 u kotów w polsce przebieg w czasie, Tech. rep. (Jul. 2023).
445 URL <http://interdisciplinary-research.eu/h5n1-u-kotow-w-polsce-prezentacje>
- 446 [21] A. Jarynowski, Spatio-temporal analysis of H5N1 in cats in Poland (citizens data), Tech. rep.
447 (Jul. 2023).
448 URL <http://rpubs.com/gulakov/1069159>
- 449 [22] A. Jarynowski, Spatio-temporal analysis of H5N1 in cats in Poland based on data from WOAHI
450 reference lab, Tech. rep. (Jul. 2023).
451 URL <https://rpubs.com/gulakov/1069204>
- 452 [23] A. Jarynowski, Spatio-temporal analysis of H5N1 in cats in Poland (comparison of sources),
453 Tech. rep. (Jul. 2023).
454 URL <https://rpubs.com/gulakov/1069216>
- 455 [24] A. Jarynowski, A. Semenov, V. Belik, Risk calculators during COVID-19 pandemic Four
456 innovative examples from Wrocław, *E-methodology* 8 (8) (2021). doi:[https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.15503/emet.2021.112.124)
457 [15503/emet.2021.112.124](https://doi.org/10.15503/emet.2021.112.124).
- 458 [25] A. Jarynowski, Phenomenon of participatory “guerilla” epidemiology in post-communist
459 European countries (2021).
460 URL <https://sites.utu.fi/bre/phenomenon-of-participatory-guerilla-epidemiology-in-pos>
- 461 [26] M. Welz, K. Śmietanka, Przewodnik stosowania rozporządzenia (UE) 2016/429 w zakresie
462 zwalczania chorób zakaźnych zwierząt, PIWeT, 2022.
- 463 [27] A. Strzelecki, A. Meinzenbach, M. Zieger, Infodemic and infodemiology in public health:
464 Similarities and differences, *Healthcare Analytics* (2023) 100243.
- 465 [28] A. Jarynowski, V. Belik, Infodemiology and infoveillance in one health mass events (case study
466 of odra ecological disaster) (2023).
- 467 [29] A. Jarynowski, Infodemiologia oraz infonadzór-doświadczenia doby pandemii, in: *Epidemiolo-*
468 *gia i bezpieczeństwo CBRN : nauka, innowacje, implikacje praktyczne*, Epimilitaris, Wojskowy
469 Instytut Techniczny Uzbrojenia, Zielonka, 2022, pp. 235–248, (eds) Anna Mróz-Jagiello,
470 Jarosław Walczak.
- 471 [30] A. Jarynowski, Ptasia grypa w mięsnym jako przykład mał-informacji, Tech. rep. (Jul. 2023).
472 URL <http://interdisciplinary-research.eu/ptasia-grypa-w-miesnym-przyklad-malinformacji>

- 473 [31] K. T. Gradoń, J. A. Hołyst, W. R. Moy, J. Sienkiewicz, K. Suchecki, Countering misinfor-
474 mation: A multidisciplinary approach, *Big Data & Society* 8 (1) (2021) 205395172110138.
475 doi:10.1177/20539517211013848.
476 URL <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/20539517211013848>
- 477 [32] A. Jarynowski, Ł. Krzowski, S. Maksymowicz, Biological mis (dis)-information in the internet
478 as a possible kremlin warfare (2023).
- 479 [33] G. Eysenbach, How to fight an infodemic: the four pillars of infodemic management, *Journal*
480 *of medical Internet research* 22 (6) (2020) e21820, publisher: JMIR Publications Inc., Toronto,
481 Canada.
- 482 [34] K. D. Nahata, F. Bielejec, J. Monetta, S. Dellicour, A. Rambaut, M. A. Suchard, G. Baele,
483 P. Lemey, Spread 4: online visualisation of pathogen phylogeographic reconstructions, *Virus*
484 *Evolution* 8 (2), veac088 (2022). doi:10.1093/ve/veac088.
485 URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/ve/veac088>
- 486 [35] Szkudlarek, A. Jarynowska, Diagnoza adaptacji i mitygacji do zmian klimatu obszaru
487 metropolitalnego gdańsk-gdynia-sopot, Tech. rep., Ekovert (2021).
488 URL https://www.metropoliagdansk.pl/upload/files/72_%20Diagnoza%20adaptacji%20i%20mitygacji%20do%20zmian%20klimatu%20Obszaru%20Metropolitalnego%20Gdańsk-Gdynia-Sopot.pdf
- 491 [36] A. Rambaut, A. J. Drummond, D. Xie, G. Baele, M. A. Suchard, Posterior summarization in
492 bayesian phylogenetics using tracer 1.7, *Systematic biology* 67 (5) (2018) 901–904.
- 493 [37] R. Paluch, Ł. G. Gajewski, J. A. Hołyst, B. K. Szymanski, Optimizing sensors placement
494 in complex networks for localization of hidden signal source: A review, *Future Generation*
495 *Computer Systems* 112 (2020) 1070–1092.
- 496 [38] X. Lu, J. Mou, B. Dai, S. Tan, P. Holme, S. Lehmann, et al., The spindle approximation of
497 network epidemiological modeling (2023).
- 498 [39] C. Gray, A. Radford, Using electronic health records to explore negotiations around euthanasia
499 decision making for dogs and cats in the uk, *Veterinary Record* 190 (9) (2022) no–no.
- 500 [40] E. Lindh, H. Lounela, N. Ikonen, T. Kantala, C. Savolainen-Kopra, A. Kauppinen, P. Öster-
501 lund, L. Kareinen, A. Katz, T. Nokireki, et al., Highly pathogenic avian influenza a (h5n1)
502 virus infection on multiple fur farms in the south and central ostrobothnia regions of finland,
503 july 2023, *Eurosurveillance* 28 (31) (2023) 2300400.
- 504 [41] A. Jarynowski, Katastrofa na Odrze ukazała dysfunkcjonalność działania instytucji państwa,
505 *Nowa Konfederacja* (2022).
506 URL <https://nowakonfederacja.pl/katastrofa-na-odrze-ukazala-dysfunkcjonalnosc-dzialani>
- 507 [42] A. Jarynowski, Agroterrorism using biological agents and its threats in poland and europe
508 in the context of covid-19 pandemic and ukraine crisis, *Terrorism, Study and Prevention*
509 (accepted) (2023).
- 510 [43] C. Stephen, J. Berezowski, Wildlife health surveillance and intelligence. challenges and op-
511 portunities, *Wildlife Population Health* (2022) 99–111.

512 [44] L. C. Falzon, J. Ogola, E. M. Fèvre, J. Berezowski, Benefits of using a transdisciplinary ap-
513 proach for the design and operationalization of a surveillance system, One Health Cases (2023)
514 (2023) ohcs20230016.